

Quinonoid molecular diversity in Bignoniaceae and its taxonomic significance[†]

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Abstract : The present brief review focus on isolation of a large number of naphthoquinones, anthraquinones and naphthoquinone dimers from more than 33 plant species of 16 genera of family Bignoniaceae. The following sixteen genera viz. *Catalpa*, *Crescentia*, *Heterophragma* (syn : *Haplophragma*), *Kigelia*, *Lundia*, *Mansoa*, *Markhamia* (syn : *Dolichandrone*), *Newbouldia*, *Oroxylum*, *Paratecoma*, *Phyllarthron*, *Radermachera*, *Stereospermum*, *Tabebuia*, *Tecomella* (syn : *Tecoma*) and *Zeyhera* have so far chemically investigated for more than sixty quinonoid constituents. Ten plant species belonging to seven genera namely *Heterophragma*, *Kigelia*, *Markhamia*, *Phyllarthron*, *Stereospermum*, *Tabebuia* and *Tecomella* have chemically been examined by our group during last three decades which have resulted in the isolation of two dozen of quinonoid compounds including some new naphthoquinones and their dimers. The structures of these compounds were unambiguously established from chemical and spectral evidences. Their taxonomic and biogenetic significance were discussed.

Keywords : Naphthoquinones, anthraquinones, naphthoquinone dimers, Bignoniaceae, taxonomy, biogenesis.

Introduction

The natural quinones are widely distributed and exist in large number and great structural variety. They are found mainly in higher plants, fungi, bacteria and in animal kingdom in arthropods and echinoderms¹. In higher plants they are located in heartwood, bark and roots. It has been noticed that most of the quinones from Bignoniaceae have a C₁₅ skeleton either C₁₀-C₅ (naphthoquinone) or C₁₄-C₁ (anthraquinone). The later are formed by cyclization of C₁₀-C₅ precursor most probably deoxylapachol (1) followed by oxidation. Benzoquinones are so far not detected from any genus of this family. Co-existence of naphtho and anthraquinones is a notable feature of this family, which has tremendous taxonomic significance. Taxonomists classify plants on the basis of characteristic morphological and anatomical features. The situation is similar in chemical taxonomy. Chemists therefore always look for characteristic pattern of compounds

in different organs. Different parts of plants normally contain different chemical constituents and a comparison of the chemistry of leaves of one species with that of roots or seeds of another species may lead to erroneous conclusion. Unfortunately the part of plants investigated is some time not mentioned in the literature, thus making the information of little taxonomic value. Further chemical composition of plants or plant organs often varies greatly with age and season²⁻⁴. The chemistry of living parts is often less constant than that of dead tissues such as heartwoods, barks, which frequently are rich sources of characteristic constituents.

Carefully looking at heartwood constituents of a large number of Bignoniaceous plants showed a remarkable parallelism between their chemistry and morphological characters. Literature survey of different plant species of genera *Catalpa*, *Crescentia*, *Heterophragma*, *Jacaranda*, *Kigelia*, *Lundia*, *Mansoa*, *Markhamia*, *Millingtonia*,

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Newbouldia, *Oroxylum*, *Paratecoma*, *Phyllarthron*, *Radermachera*, *Stereospermum*, *Tabebuia*, *Tecomella* and *Zeyhera* displayed the presence of lapachol, their congeners and anthraquinones with exception of *Millingtonia hortensis* and *Jacaranda mimosaeifolia*. Quinonoid components isolated from various species of above genera are listed below. The isolation of deoxylapachol (1), 2-methyl-3-prenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (2), α -lapachone (7), 4-hydroxy- α -lapachone (10), 9-methoxy- α -lapachone (9), 4,9-dihydroxy- α -lapachone (11), 8-hydroxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (21), 3,8-dihydroxydehydroiso- α -lapachone

(22), 8-hydroxy-2-isopropenyl[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (42), and 1-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone (57) from wood and tissue culture of *Catalpa ovata*⁵⁻⁹; lapachol (3), β -lapachone (13), and emodin (61) from stem wood of *Catalpa longissima*¹⁰; 5-hydroxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (19), 5-methoxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (20), 5,6-dimethoxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (24), (2*S*,3*S*)-3-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (27), kigelinone (31), isokigelinone (32), 3-hydroxymethyl furo[3,2-*b*]naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-5,10-quinone (43), and its 9-hydroxy derivative (44) from wood of *Crescentia cujete*¹¹⁻¹³; lapachol (3), α -lapachone (7), β -lapachone (13), dehydro- α -lapachone (14), tecomaquinone-I (45), dilapachone (48), and adenophyllone (49) from heartwood of *Heterophragma adenophyllum*¹⁴⁻¹⁶; quadrilone (50) from heartwood of *Heterophragma quadriloculare*¹⁷;

- 1; R = H
2; R = Me
3; R = OH
4; R = OMe
5; R = -CH₂-CH=C(Me)₂

- 7; R¹=R²=H
8; R¹=OH, R²=H
9; R¹=OMe, R²=H
10; R¹=H, R²=OH
11; R¹=R²=OH
12; R¹=OMe, R²=OH

6

13

- 14; R = H
15; R = OH

- 17; R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=H
18; R¹=OH, R²=R³=R⁴=H
19; R¹=H, R²=OH, R³=R⁴=H
20; R¹=H, R²=OMe, R³=R⁴=H
21; R¹=R²=R³=H, R⁴=OH
22; R¹=R⁴=OH, R²=R³=H
23; R¹=OH, R³=OMe, R²=R⁴=H
24; R¹=H, R²=R³=OMe, R⁴=H
25; R¹=R³=OMe, R²=R⁴=H
26; R¹=R²=OH, R³=OMe, R⁴=H
27; R¹=OH, R²=R³=OMe, R⁴=H

16

- 28; R¹=-CH₂-CH₃, R²=R³=R⁴=R⁵=H
29; R¹=-CH(OH)CH₃, R²=R³=R⁴=R⁵=H
30; R¹=-CH₂CH₃, R²=R³=R⁴=H, R⁵=OH
31; R¹=-CH(OH)CH₃, R²=R³=R⁴=H, R⁵=OH
32; R¹=-CH(OH)CH₃, R²=OH, R³=R⁴=R⁵=H
33; R¹=-CH(OH)CH₃, R²=R³=H, R⁴=R⁵=OMe
34; R¹=-CH(OH)CH₃, R²=R³=OH, R⁴=R⁵=H
35; R¹=-CH(OH)CH₃, R²=OH, R³=OMe, R⁴=R⁵=H
36; R¹=-COCH₃, R²=R³=R⁴=R⁵=H
37; R¹=-COCH₃, R²=R³=R⁴=H, R⁵=OH
38; R¹=-COCH₃, R²=OH, R³=R⁴=R⁵=H
39; R¹=-COCH₃, R²=OMe, R³=R⁴=R⁵=H
40; R¹=-COCH₃, R²=R³=H, R⁴=R⁵=OMe
41; R¹=-C(Me)=CH₂, R²=R³=R⁴=R⁵=H
42; R¹=-C(Me)=CH₂, R²=R³=R⁴=H, R⁵=OH

- 43; R = H
44; R = OH

lapachol (3), dehydro- α -lapachone (14), and kigelinone (31) from roots and heartwood of *Kigelia pinnata*¹⁸⁻²⁰; α -caryopterone (15) from wood of *Lundia densiflora*²¹; 4-hydroxy-9-methoxy- α -lapachone (12) from wood of *Mansoa alliacea*²²; α -lapachone (7), dehydro- α -lapachone (14) and 2-isopropenyl-naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (41) from wood of *Markhamia hildebrandtii*²³; lapachol (3), β -lapachone (13) and dehydroiso- α -lapachone (17) from wood of *Markhamia platyalyx*²⁴; lapachol (3), β -lapachone (13), dehydro- α -lapachone (14) and tecomaquinone-I (45) from heartwood of *Markhamia stipulata*²⁴; dehydro- α -lapachone (14) and 3-hydroxy-dehydroiso- α -lapachone (18) from root bark of *Newbouldia laevis*²⁵; dehydroiso- α -lapachone (17) from *Oroxylum indicum*²⁶; lapachol (3), β -lapachone (13), dehydro- α -lapachone (14) and tecomaquinone-I (45) from heartwood of *Phyllarthron comorense*²⁷; lapachol (3), dehydro- α -lapachone (14), dehydroiso- α -lapachone (17), 3-hydroxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (18), (2*S*,3*S*)-3-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (27), 3-hydroxy-6-methoxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (23), 3,6-dimethoxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (25) and 3,5-dihydroxy-6-methoxydehydroiso- α -lapachone (26) from wood of *Radermachera sinica*⁷; lapachol (3) from aerial parts of *Stereospermum kunthianum*²⁸; lapachol (3), dehydro- α -lapachone (14) and tecomaquinone-I (45) from aerial parts of *Stereospermum suaveolens*²⁹; 2-methyl-3-

prenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (2), lapachol (3), lapachol methyl ether (4), α -lapachone (7), β -lapachone (13), dehydro- α -lapachone (14), tactoquinone (51), 2-hydroxymethylanthraquinone (52), 2-acetoxymethylanthraquinone (53), anthraquinone-2-aldehyde (54), anthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid (55), 1-hydroxyanthraquinone (56), 3-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone (58) and tabebuina (62) from heartwood of *Tabebuia avellaneda*^{30,31}; 2-(1-hydroxyethyl)naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (29), kigelinone (31), and 2-acetylnaphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (36) from stem bark of *Tabebuia cassinoides*³²; 1-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone (57), 3-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone (58) and tecomaquinone-I (45) from heartwood of *Tabebuia chrysantha*³³; lapachol (3) from the wood of *Tabebuia flavescens*³⁴; 2,3-diprenyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (5), β -lapachone (13) and dehydro- α -lapachone (14) from heartwood of *Tabebuia guayacan*^{35,36}; 2-(1-hydroxyethyl)naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (29), kigelinone (31) and 5-hydroxy-2-(1-hydroxyethyl)naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (32) from wood of *Tabebuia impetiginosa*^{37,38}; dehydroiso- α -lapachone (17), 5-hydroxy-2-(1-hydroxyethyl)-6-methoxynaphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (35) and tecomaquinone-I (45) from trunk wood of *Tabebuia incana*³⁹; lapachol (3), β -lapachone (13), 2-(1-hydroxyethyl)-7,8-dimethoxynaphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (33) and 2-acetyl-7,8-dimethoxynaphtho[2,3-

b]furan-4,9-quinone (40) from wood of *Tabebuia ochraceae*⁴⁰; lapachol (3), α -lapachone (7), dehydro- α -lapachone (14), α -ethylfurano-1,4-naphthoquinone (28), tecomaquinone-I (45), tecomaquinone-II (46) and tecomaquinone-III (47) from heartwood of *Tabebuia pentaphylla*⁴¹⁻⁴⁵; lapachol (3), dehydro- α -lapachone (14), dehydroiso- α -lapachone (17), tecomaquinone-I (45), tecomaquinone-III (47) and tabebuin (62) from bark and heartwood of *Tabebuia rosea*⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹; lapachol (3), β -lapachone (13), dehydroiso- α -lapachone (17), 2-isopropenyl-naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (41) and tecomaquinone-I (45) from wood of *Tabebuia serratifolia*⁵⁰; deoxylapachol (1), lapachol (3), α -lapachone (7), β -lapachone (13), dehydro- α -lapachone (14), 2-isopropenyl-naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (41) and tecomaquinone-I (45) from heartwood of *Tecomella undulata*^{14, 51-53}; lapachol (3) from wood of *Zeyhera digitalis*⁵⁴; lapachol (3), α -lapachone (7), 4-hydroxy- α -lapachone (10) and dehydro- α -lapachone (14) from the wood of *Zeyhera tuberculosa*⁵⁵; lapachol (3), lomatiol (6), dehydroiso- α -lapachone (17), α -ethylfurano-1,4-naphthoquinone (28), β -methylpyrano-1,4-naphthoquinone (16) and 2-(1-hydroxyethyl)naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-quinone (29) from heartwood of *Paratecoma peroba*^{56,57}.

Chemotaxonomic studies

Prior to the chromatographic era often only one or two compounds were isolated from each species investigated. Now the major components are found to be accompanied by a plethora of minor compounds. Even trace compounds may be important if the same or related compounds occur in botanically related species. Failure to detect an expected compound does not necessarily mean that it is absent, for even the present analytical methods have their limitations. The isolation of a large number of naphtho- and anthraquinones and naphthoquinone dimers from various genus of Bignoniaceae implies that these compounds are characteristic of this family. Lapachol has been reported almost from each genus so far investigated as a major component and hence it may be concluded that it is a chemical marker of this family. All these quinones are biogenetically related. Quite often identical compounds have been found to occur in unrelated plants and this phenomenon has been one of the main objections to molecular taxonomy. In fact it is not at all surprising that enzymatic prerequisites for the biosynthesis of identical compounds have been developed in unrelated organisms. The probability of identical compounds, however, is much greater in related taxa.

Biogenetic studies

Quinone biosynthesis shows a very diversified pic-

ture. The higher quinones arise by polyketide or shikimic-mevalonic acid mixed pathways. The anthraquinones present in heartwoods of Bignoniaceous plants^{33,58} are accompanied by a large number of C₁₅ naphthoquinones including deoxylapachol (**1**). Deoxylapachol (**1**) is synthesized *in vivo* by prenylation of naphthol precursor followed by oxidation and since deoxylapachol can also be converted into 2-methylanthraquinone (**51**) *in vitro*, either by boron trifluoride catalysis or by irradiation, it looks likely that the substituted (C) ring in this group of anthraquinones is derived from mevalonate. This was established by feeding *Rubia tintorum* plant (Rubiaceae) with [2-C¹⁴] mevalonate⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ and presumably the same pathway is followed in the Bignoniaceae. The "C₁₀ precursor" has still to be identified it could be α -naphthol but a search for this compound was unsuccessful. Some more work has to be required to establish this hypothesis.

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